

Questionnaire COVID-19

You have been selected to participate in this research as a stakeholder in choosing measures to prevent the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. The present study aims to develop and apply a multi-criteria and participatory model for the decision-making process in pandemic responses, in conditions of increased uncertainty.

The study includes 2 rounds of consultations with stakeholders, the first round being undertaken in November 2020. Participation in this study is voluntary, anonymous, and the duration of completing the survey is 1-5 minutes.

This consultation is a part of a project funded by European Open Science Cloud EOSC, Covid-19 Fast Track Funding, and led by Innovating Governance, a non-profit organization in Vienna, Austria, whose team consists of international researchers affiliated with numerous prestigious academic institutions. Find out more about us here: <https://www.igovernance.eu/about>.

Innovating Governance will retain the data provided only for their processing and interpretation, without distributing them to third parties. The results of this questionnaire will be presented publicly only in the form of useful analyses and interpretations for the decision-making model.

Continuing and completing this questionnaire is your consent for the collection, storage, and processing of the information you provide by Innovating Governance.

For any questions about this research or technical issues of the questionnaire, please contact us at adriana.mihai@iis.unibuc.ro. Thank you for your participation and interest.

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* Required

1. In what activity sector are you currently working? *

Mark only one oval.

- Government / Public administration
- Healthcare / social care system
- Education and research
- Non-governmental sector
- Private sector
- Other: _____

Ranking measures

The different measures which can be taken to mitigate the SARS-CoV-2 epidemic in Jordan can be pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical. The present study analyzes 4 different types of mitigation strategies, summed up in the following sets of measures:

- MEASURES 1: only pharmaceutical measures (treatments, vaccination)**
MEASURES 2: pharmaceutical measures, temporary school and workplace closures
MEASURES 3: pharmaceutical measures, social distancing recommended
MEASURES 4: pharmaceutical measures and social distancing imposed (lockdown)

Any chosen set of mitigation measures impacts various areas of life, which include health, education, human development, mental health and wellbeing. The project team has estimated the impact of every measure set above upon each of these areas in Jordan, for 2020-2021.

1. Which measure set do you think is better if you take into consideration their estimated effects on DIRECT FATALITIES? Please rank the measure sets from the worst (1) to the best (10).

MEASURE SETS	IMPACT: DIRECT FATALITIES*
MEASURES 1	Between 18,648 and 22,792
MEASURES 2	Between 15,800 and 19,312
MEASURES 3	Between 11,217 and 13,709
MEASURES 4	Between 7,435 and 9,087

*based on epidemiologic modelling, demographic and epidemiologic data from statistical reports published by the Ministry of Health, Jordan

15. Measures 2 *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

16. Measures 3 *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

17. Measures 4 *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Ranking criteria

According to your perception of their relative importance, rank the criteria from 1 to 9 below. For instance, if a criterion has rank 9, it is more important than a criterion with rank 8, which in turn, is significantly more important than a criterion with rank 5, etc. Several criteria can have the same importance rank.

18. Direct fatalities *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

19. School days lost *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

20. Human development *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

21. Mental health and well-being *

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

Thank you for your participation!

22. Thank you for your time. For any questions or comments, please use the text box below or send us an email at adriana.mihai@lts.unibuc.ro.

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